

Editor/Author Correspondence

Editor
2023-10-25 02:06 AM

Subject: [CENDEKIA] Editor Decision [DELETE](#)

Ahmad Juhaidi:

We have reached a decision regarding your submission to Cendekia: Jurnal Kependidikan dan Kemasyarakatan, "The Perceived Utility and University Enrolment Intention in Indonesia (A High School and Islamic High School Student Perspective)".

Our decision is to:

Fata Asyrofi Yahya
IAIN Ponorogo
asyrofi@iainponorogo.ac.id
Jurnal Cendekia IAIN Ponorogo

Author
2023-10-25 01:46 PM

Subject: The Perceived Utility and University Enrolment Intention in Indonesia (A High School and Islamic High School Student Perspective) [DELETE](#)

Dear Editor

I would like to thank the reviewers for their insightful feedback. All changes for reviewer A are highlighted in yellow in the main text.

Comment 1:

The words 'High School and Islamic High School' should be removed, and the title should be reworded as follows: "The Perceived Utility and University Enrolment Intention in Indonesia: Students Perspective". This title will be simpler and more interesting, because the explanation of student identity is already in the research method

Response:

Revisions have been made

Comment 2:

Please, be careful in the use of terms. You should only use terms that are standardized and often used in general, such as general higher education (GHE). Because the term secular is very interpretive. For example, in language, the term secular is not related to religion, but in GHE in Indonesia, religious material is still taught, even though the name is not an Islamic university.

Response:

A term change has been made

Comment 3:

Try to make this sentence more systematic, because one word (cost) is in material form. While the other (proved) is in the form of a verb, synchronize again.

Response:

The necessary synchronize have been made.

Comment 4:

Readjust the use of the term SHE to GHE. And Correct the writing of the page numbers in the references of the journal article marked in red in the footnotes. The page numbering should be from small to large numbers, not the other way around.

Response:

The necessary adjustments have been made

Comment 5:

You should use footnotes instead of innotes. Please, adjust the pattern again like the others.

Response:

The necessary revision have been made

Comment 6:

Correct the writing of the page numbers in the references of the journal article marked in red in the footnotes. The page numbering should be from small to large numbers, not the other way around.

Response:

The necessary correction have been made

Comment 7:

The wording of this sentence is awkward and needs to be corrected, where it was previously said that SHE is not seen in terms of usefulness when students graduate, and IHE is seen in terms of usefulness when students graduate. But why does the conclusion suddenly emphasize that the usefulness of IHE when students graduate is not widely considered?

Response:

The necessary correction have been made

Jurnal Cendekia IAIN Ponorogo

Author
2023-11-12 04:32 AM

Subject: The Perceived Utility and University Enrolment Intention in Indonesia (A High School and Islamic High School Student Perspective) [DELETE](#)

Dear Editor

I would like to thank the reviewers for their insightful feedback. All changes for reviewer A are highlighted in yellow, for reviewer B are highlighted in blue, for

reviewer C are highlighted in bright green, and for editor in brown in the main text.

REVIEWER A

Comment 1:

The words 'High School and Islamic High School' should be removed, and the title should be reworded as follows: "The Perceived Utility and University Enrolment Intention in Indonesia: Students Perspective". This title will be simpler and more interesting, because the explanation of student identity is already in the research method

Response:

Revisions have been made

Comment 2:

Please, be careful in the use of terms. You should only use terms that are standardized and often used in general, such as general higher education (GHE). Because the term secular is very interpretive. For example, in language, the term secular is not related to religion, but in GHE in Indonesia, religious material is still taught, even though the name is not an Islamic university.

Response:

A term change has been made

Comment 3:

Try to make this sentence more systematic, because one word (cost) is in material form. While the other (proved) is in the form of a verb, synchronize again.

Response:

The necessary synchronize have been made.

Comment 4:

Readjust the use of the term SHE to GHE. And Correct the writing of the page numbers in the references of the journal article marked in red in the footnotes. The page numbering should be from small to large numbers, not the other way around.

Response:

The necessary adjustments have been made

Comment 5:

You should use footnotes instead of innotes. Please, adjust the pattern again like the others.

Response:

The necessary revisions have been made

Comment 6:

Correct the writing of the page numbers in the references of the journal article marked in red in the footnotes. The page numbering should be from small to large numbers, not the other way around.

Response:

The necessary corrections have been made

Comment 7:

The wording of this sentence is awkward and needs to be corrected, where it was previously said that SHE is not seen in terms of usefulness when students graduate, and IHE is seen in terms of usefulness when students graduate. But why does the conclusion suddenly emphasize that the usefulness of IHE when students graduate is not widely considered?

Response:

The necessary corrections have been made
Jurnal Cendekia IAIN Ponorogo

REVIEWER B

Komentar 1:

Ditambah penulis luar negeri, serta gunakan template yang ada di cendekia

Respon

Telah ditambah dan disesuaikan dengan template.

Komentar 2:

Footnote diletakkan setelah titik, tolong diperbaiki footnote yang belum sesuai, serta rapikan pada masing-masing, sesuaikan font footnote juga

Respon

Perbaikan telah dilakukan

Komentar 3:

Tabel sesuaikan template dan perbaiki tabelnya

Respon

Telah disesuaikan dengan template

Komentar 4:

Jabarkan dalam bentuk deskripsi dan tidak boleh menggunakan numbering

Respon

Perbaikan telah dilakukan

Komentar 5:

Rapikan daftar pustakanya

Respon

Perbaikan telah dilakukan

REVIEWER C

Comment 1:
the validity and reliability of the instrument
Response
The requested revisions have been made

Comment 2
The data analysis is not thorough enough. The authors do not present any statistical tests to support their claims.
Response
Revisions have been made

Comment 3
The authors make several claims not supported by the evidence they present.
Response
Revisions have been made

EDITOR

Comment 1:
Abstrak terdiri dari 150-200 kata yang berisi tujuan, metode, dan hasil atau temuan.
Respon
Perbaikan telah dilakukan

Comment 2:
Perbanyak kutipan dari artikel jurnal terutama jurnal Cendekia dan jurnal-jurnal internasional terindeks scopus.
Respon
Literatur telah ditambah

Comment 3:
Tambahkan penulis dari luar negeri.
Respon
Penulis telah ditambah

Best Regard
Ahmad Juhaidi
Jurnal Cendekia IAIN Ponorogo

Editor
2023-11-15 08:20 AM

Subject: [CENDEKIA] Editor Decision [DELETE](#)

Ahmad Juhaidi:

We have reached a decision regarding your submission to Cendekia: Jurnal Kependidikan dan Kemasyarakatan, "The Perceived Utility and University Enrolment Intention in Indonesia (A High School and Islamic High School Student Perspective)".

Our decision is to:

Fata Asyrofi Yahya
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